

Analysis of Observation Results Preventing Children's/ Adventures' Delinquency in The Environment Around Semarang State University

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ABSTRACT

Research This aim for (1) as effort For ward off mischief child / adolescent in a way wise , precise , and efficient which is topic the discussion presented in study this (2) in order to obtain addition input for K produce increasing therapy _ accurate for educators _ especially , leaders public generally in develop source Power quality human being through humanities (sciences For advance human) so reach true humanity . _ Study This is study descriptive qualitative . Research setting it's in the environment around UNNES, subject study This is children / adolescents in the environment around UNNES. Tools or instrument study researcher role active in obtaining data in the field . Data collection techniques used covers observation and documentation.

INTRODUCTION

The term delinquency originate from the basic word "naughty" (Javanese), which is nominally/ literally appear from the word "ana akali" meaning "to exist. "sense or arise his wits". A child small that started arise reason / thought own Spirit want to know the big one For imitate, for example follow take glass or plate from on table, but Because not enough ability and not yet thought the consequences He can drop the glass / plate he grabbed the until broken messy. Consequence things that don't thought the He Can hit angry Because considered violate norm social (solve, harm), even sometimes forced pinched by his mother and if done repeatedly _ He will get predicate "child naughty". Prof. DR. Fuad Hasan said that "Delinquency" is anti-social acts committed by children / adolescents who _ done by adults qualified as follow crime. MA Merrill in his book Problems of Child Delinquency stated: "A child is classified as a delinquent when his anti-social tendencies appear to someone to be so grave that he becomes or ought to become the subject of official action" or a child classified as when delinquent exists looks trend Such antisocial_ culminating and giving rise disturbances so the authorities forced take action towards him with road arrest and exile him. From opinion the can withdrawn conclusion, that element deed delinquent ie violation norm society, so nature antisocial, and as action For secure society - rikat, them needs to be "secured" so that it doesn't harm society. Another similar opinion said, that deed delinquent is all the act which is interrupter - wengan norms group certain things that give rise to it trouble in society carried out by children young.

The problem of "Juvenile Delinquency" is frequent give rise to worry social Because the excess can give rise to possible "generation gap", because expected children _ as cadres successor as well as candidates leader many nations (revitalizing agents). slipped in mud humiliation, like bud falling flowers _ before blossom scatter fragrant.

However, perhaps We Agree, mischief child as something characteristic natural / natural (like lightning, mountains eruptions, floods, storms, and so on) no can dammed / eliminated, but only simply Can denied with ways / efforts in a way wise, so No fatal consequences as well harm public a lot. Researcher feel interested For do study ward off mischief child / adolescent reviewed from facet observations in the environment around UNNES.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

Study This including to in study descriptive qualitative. Subject study This is children / adolescents in the environment around UNNES. Object research studied _ is observation mischief children / adolescents in the environment around UNNES. The data source is: analysis observation mischief children / adolescents in the environment about UNNES and documents. Data in the form of taking pictures results observation. Research tools or instruments researcher role active in obtaining data in the field. Data collection techniques used covers observation and documentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As base or step beginning in analyze the data later next with the observation process or observation , so discovered by the observation process according to data sources and according to experts . Following results study form description ward off mischief children / teenagers who have explained in accordance with research , as well the discussion .

Understanding

Drs. B. Simanjuntak, SH believes that Not yet There is term technical in Indonesian for _ gives the meaning of " juvenile delinquency ". Juvenile delinquency translates as " crime. " child " has effect psychology that doesn't Good for children that . Children feel himself has stamped with predicate evil , which gives rise to isolation self . Whereas criteria used _ For stamp it is adult criteria . _ While we are know that children it's not man mature small , so they in do Not yet can think about consequences negative that would be happens , okay to himself or to society . They Not yet feel that Act he did That wrong Because motivation from his actions Not yet realized as condition from something action , often the motive of action children different with the motives of the parents ' actions . Difference view this is often the case cause happen difference opinion between adults _ with children young . A child who violates norm social Not yet can said wicked Because He Not yet realize norm social .

It turned out to be a case of juvenile delinquent It's everywhere, it's proven exists term special for him , as in Germany it is called wohlfarts criminaliteit ; in the United States called rebels without a cause; in England called teddy boys; in Sweden is mentioned skinn knutte ; in France called blousons noire ; in the Netherlands it is called Stoute jongens / keerels , and if more increase called baldaardige keerels ; in Japan called taiyosoku .

From several the meaning above can withdrawn conclusion that juvenile delinquency is deed children who violate norm social , norm law , norm group , and annoying peace society , so the authorities forced take action security / deterrence . (If the delinquency is carried out by an adult / elderly person called crime .)

Age limit (children) for determining juvenile delinquent, apparently Not yet There are strict limits in various countries, including :

- 1) According to the Criminal Code Articles 45-47 states that " not yet mature his age not yet 16 years old ."
- 2) In the United States according to Prof. Car A. Eliot Ph.D., some area set age child teenagers under 16, 17, 18 years old currently in two areas other stipulate under 21 years of age .
- 3) At BINAPTA (Guidance for Children, Youth and Women) Bandung, apparently children fostered on site _ the Because do mischief range between 10 years old up to 21 years .
- 4) In England the age limit for "juvenile delinquent" is 8 years to below , in Denmark 15 years to below , while the 1955 seminar in Rio De Janeiro set the age limit for juvenile delinquents at 14 years .

- 5) Views from psychology (DR. Kohnstamm) the age limit for juvenile delinquent is more skewed by age prepubertal (14 years) to adolescence (18 years).

A number of Actions Child Delinquency

From the description above has is known that deed mischief is acts that violate / misappropriate norm social / group certain causes _ trouble or bother peace society , so that the authorities forced take action security . Actions that have been done I get it from activity observations in the environment around UNNES _ including :

- a) Speeding , that is drive vehicle with surpassing speed _ speed specified maximum , so _ can annoying / harmful user another way . (Speed maximum inside _ city is 25 to 40 kilometers per hour.)
- b) Circulation pornography among _ student , fine in form Images obscene , magazines , and pornographic stories that can be damaging children's morals , up to circulation medicines stimulant lust sexual , contraceptive , and so on .
- c) Kids like it _ make destruction to goods or someone else 's , like take guava / mango "Pak Raden", make annoying doodles _ beauty environment , holding sabotage , and so on .
- d) Shaping group or alley with scary norms , like _ group tattooed , group get dressed disheveled , and so on .
- e) Get dressed with no mode aligned with appetite environment , so seen less / no polite to the eye the environment .
- f) Happy children _ _ see other people in trouble consequence his actions and deeds , such as make hole or sow seeds - seeds peanut green / soy black on the road or sprinkle oil on the road , so Lots drivers who fall / slip and fall smeared oil , arrived injury hence .
- g) Annoying / taunting people who pass in front of him , and if turned / angry A little just considered make because to " do ".
- h) And still Lots Again type mischief committed by children _ young .

A number of Reason Mischief

By phenomenological looks that symptom mischief arise in puberty / transition , where the soul in circumstances unstable , so easy dragged by the environment . (Still profitable when dragged / affected by conditions positive from environment .) A child No suddenly become naughty , but become naughty Because a number of moment after shaped by the environment (family , school , community), incl outside opportunities _ control namely :

- a) Environment broken family , less _ attention , less love Dear , because each of them is busy with his business individually (incl look for living For fulfil need life everyday).
- b) Situation (home stairs , school , environment) which is boring and boring , even though places the it should can is factor important For prevent mischief for children (incl poor environment _ recreational).
- c) Environment people who don't / don't uncertain for prospect future life , such as full society _ speculation , corruption , manipulation , gossip , rumors negative / destructive , difference too striking between the rich and the poor, and so on .

Symptoms Mischief

Symptom Act in demand child showing _ or leads to action mischief must can detected as early as maybe , because when Act he did has crossed the line, then Finally child No capable Again face himself Alone in life healthy society . _ As for the symptoms that lead to to deed mischief including :

- a) Always a child alone Because No liked by his friends (ostracized) can _ suffer disturbance emotions , therefore He need quite a bit of attention special from parents , teachers, or member people who know about it , for made him aware How get along the best with avoid attitude arrogant / haughty , words that can hurtful heart , cynical , insulting , and so on .
- b) Children often _ _ avoid self from not quite enough answer at home / school . This thing usually caused Because child No enjoy assigned work _ to him , so He distance self from busyness home / school , and search other activities that don't guided or not supervised .
- c) Frequent children complaining / fretting Because experience the problem is not solved by him myself , so as a result can carried away by the shock lingering emotions.
- d) Frequent children prejudiced that their parents / teachers behave No Good towards him and on purpose hinder himself .
- e) Children who don't capable center attention / thoughts them (concentrating), because exists shock emotions about him .
- f) Children who experience it phobias and excessive anxiety , so _ different with afraid other normal children .
- g) Frequent children hurt and annoy his friends , both at home as well as at school .
- h) A child who likes lying or said fake / cheat .
- i) Children who feel No valued results his efforts , because he is an adult has set / put too goal _ hard For achieved child . Consequence his boredom they then do it dangerous things _ For interesting adult attention . _ For anticipate matter This give proportional tasks (start _ from the easy ones first , then rather difficult , even difficult . _ For example , giving questions math , no direct give very difficult question) .
- j) Kids who like it skipping class because I'm lazy to study or No like eye lesson certain (note also children the truant who became source transmission disease playing truant) . For holding teachers eye lesson it is recommended that you do so convey material lesson with attract / please the students so that always Liked , easy absorbed , and digested . Take your pick methods teaching or appropriate instructional strategies _ accompanied mastery of 10 competencies professional Indonesian teachers with OK , incl utilize educational media in a way professional .

Possible Policies _ Done For Ward off Mischief

May we agree , through our Tri Education Center (family , school , community) . can do in a way together and shoulder to shoulder in ward off mischief child / adolescent with full wisdom to achieve it objective glorious with as small a risk as possible , both by educators , parents , leaders community , religious leaders , enforcers law , expert law , doctors , psychologists , and officials government , in fact preventive nor in a way curative / repressive .

a. In the family

Family is environment primary and fundamental education . That's where it is child raised , acquired invention early , as well learning is possible development self next . There are also children first of all obtain chance For appreciate it meeting / socializing with fellow humans , even obtain first protection . _ DR. Joseph S. Roucek say that family is cradle from personality or the family is the cradle of the personality . Family is center calm life and the most vital home base . If one of them member family suffer disturbance thought or frustrated , then (usually) with " go home village/ kennel " and with nostalgic , he can obtain return excitement his life . Family as center education and center culture as well as religious center , because That connection between member family must always harmonious and integrated as well as full mutual cooperation as well as love darling . Every member family must feel tranquility , joy , security , and comfort in family . Every problem family should solved through discussion reach consensus in unity opinion . On the contrary when family start cracked especially broken (broken home) , then that's where it is source mischief child . Although husband and wife Busy work outside _ House look for livelihood , however attention as well as love love parents _ to his son still not can neglected , so as not to become reason emergence mischief .

Situation family to always be recreational and not boring - right. Creation all over member compact family _ in look after busyness healthy family _ with the manners of life harmonious family , to be dream main . Formations healthy habits (habit formations) , giving tasks that are commensurate and rewarding success , will creates a feeling of comfort as well as at home in family , as well distance happen shock emotion . Parents / substitute parents _ _ as role model family , besides notice things as it has been said , preferably in take policy as well as ward off mischief member his family pay attention too following : (globally)

1. If parents hear / see the child is " speeding " , then besides give explanations about risk / danger or consequences act the invite him For watched race motorbike/ car racing or grastrack , even when Possible invite him follow train race so that possibility will overshadowed his wish in supervision , or become horrified will as a result , up to concluded that following vehicle _ polite polite

passed traffic that has a valid driver's license more profitable rather than wrong rules / norms .

2. For ward off circulation pornography should improved circulation readings quality (title , content , illustrations , paper , printing , etc.) is appropriate tastes / interests children / adolescents , p This will give rise to interest read high . _ Parents , teachers and leaders _ society to always be guide in a way continuous sons / daughters _ with painstaking and "Tut wuri handayani " . Welcome and give books support Study as well as nature add knowledge in a way positive .
3. Ward off kids like it make damage , graffiti , sabotage , and so on , ie with invite fill in time free they with meaningful activities , such as recreational events _ _ family , following race painting children , plant plant ornamental in a pot for creates affection for plants , nurtures them animals favorite For develop compassion for animals and each other _ _ creature live , hold a lottery event family For create a feeling of love for freshness useful fruits _ for health , organizing activities productive-recreative other like sports , work devotion , planting plant medicine , keeping ornamental fish , and so on .
4. Ward off participation child in group "alley", with fill in various busyness family with mutual cooperation , as well grow attitude price - respect and cooperation , mutual giving (paying attention), tolerance , and so on .
5. Improve faith and piety towards God Almighty with include in activities _ _ religion / recitation / prayer , so that it doesn't easy wobbly to various temptation as well as trial live . Increase tolerance , tolerance yourself , darling to others , be aware law , and believe truth law of karma (goods who planted it corn Certain will reap it in a way doubled double) .
6. Relating with problem mischief children who (possibly) enter in the prescientific theory , then detection to possibility is / is not exists influence / entry spirit evil , yes submitted to psychologists _ or the closest psychic . Thank goodness every parent / teacher can build self become psychologists _ or paranormal. Actually paranormal is not something that is / belongs to shirk or cheating on God, but precisely the people who (only) carry it out God's mandate is appropriate His rewards and gifts , based on each religion/ belief . The proof Enough lots of pilgrims/ paranormal priests around us . So hame Don't reckless For set somebody That sports activities _ spirit wicked or no , if not yet / not can detect about yes / no exists spirit smooth . And actually knowledge about existence spirit fine That still scientific but paranormal style.

7. Ward off deed mischief the child did it whatever me (freedom of the will), parents need always show example (Ing ngarsa sung tuladha) that neither do they whatever I in deed everyday , everyone follow the rules as well as culture society that applies and is upheld height , and rules as well as culture This need informed and explained in a way rational accompanied sanctions for the offender . Because living in accordance with the applicable rules / more halal safe than violate applicable rules / norms .
 8. Examples in films/ soap operas can picked For ward off various delinquency (for example Si Midun , Black Steel Knight, and so on). According to Goddard (1914), people whose intelligence low usually easy simple and easy _ _ affected to direction mischief until deeds violation . So people who are " mentally retarded " should quick get a good education .
 9. Pay attention , supervision as well as suggestions from parents who encourage them to be clever choose good company , so no slipped in valley miserable .
 10. On vacation long (chess monthly / semester) parents as BP3 members should Work The same with teachers, so that as long as student holidays _ get task structured (work home) which is light But useful , so it's not all over his holiday used For relax (outside home), but work in a way positive too.
 11. Parents need fast responsive to symptoms mischief as has mentioned in advance , so that early can done deterrence to his children . If necessary , collaborate with parties related , such as his teachers , rulers local experts / psychologists / psychiatrists , and so on .
- b. In the environment school
- Every education imply that education as a socialization process child in environment social . Culture/ culture academic , critical and creative , as well sportsmanship is a must built with good for its creation stability emotion so that No easy shake and stir leading excesses _ to deeds dangerous as well as mischief . According to research , if compared to with children who don't mischievous , in general child naughty looks backward in education his school . By quantitative child naughty recorded around 18% don't school , late school around 54%, and in total qualitative child naughty often truancy , less sincerity learn , more brave cheating , and so on . There is typical tendencies _ that child naughty not enough want to continue studies to more level _ tall compared with children who don't naughty . Most child naughty want to fast work and earn living . A number of thing that can be collected as reason low interest Study children naughty include :

- 1) Likes to cheat time Study For less activities _ _ _ useful , like staying up late , by the way blank while smoke or drinks hard , until abuse narcotics / drugs forbidden , pills koplo , and so on . as a result concentrate his thoughts become weak Because not enough sleep / rest , like daydreaming dreams empty , addicted , and so on . Act deterrence in a way preventive is guard harmony connection between civitas academics with involve him in busyness small until busyness big that produces successful , so No causes a feeling of brokenness Spirit or hatred to tasks , esp tasks _ _ academic . By curative / repressive must done healing to perpetrator abuse narcotics with treatments in a way medical nor in a way traditional , that is with give drink coconut water green fresh young (new picked) and not dropped from tree (so as not to happen contraction) in a way continuous (each morning / afternoon / evening) for 7 to 9 days successively , as drug bidder poisoning . Furthermore give it productive activities _ success For return confidence in himself , accompanied attention (sorta special) as well love darling , with full patience and persistence .
- 2) Likes to procrastinate time learn . For face case sort of this , in fact preventive can done with awaken will necessity notice the saying : " Never delay till tomorrow, what you can do today " continued with " Regret formerly income , regret Then not useful ." That is show importance , every child always aware will his duties and obligations for his happiness in the future day . More from that is also necessary notice proverb : " Assembly _ to upstream , swimming around to edge " . It is best to use it for watching TV and listening to the radio as entertainment / recreation when Already tired learn . And deep matter This government (cq . Department Lighting) is necessary notice arrangement TV/radio broadcasts up to give opportunities for students Study with diligent . All preparations / arrangements Study must done by the students themselves , as the saying goes in Language Japanese which says : " Zibun no koto wa zibun de suru " or " affairs Alone must done alone too", for embed deep responsibility _ as well as discipline self to child as formation habituation , which comes later will make his second nature (Dutch: Gewoonte is de tweede natuur , or habit is second nature) . By curative can carried out by a teacher order the students quick finish the tasks he faces . The methods used _ is through characteristic ways _ persuasive , command soft , until order hard (if necessary) . Finally the teacher got it show that success in every business will is satisfaction separately . If something business forced failed , then means persistence his business need improved , because in fact , failure only is delayed success _ just .
- 3) Likes playing truant or leave lesson curse _ _ student left behind lesson , or lost part important from lessons , more so when lesson

That nature prerequisite (eg mathematics), then loss - loss That will the more became the " scourge " of his studies .

By preventive recommended to teachers to improve his professionalism in PBM so teaching more interesting interest Study students , okay in a way methodological nor Because use of multimedia as well tool popular and innovative - creative displays . That 's really cool if PBM increases interesting , tendency For skipping class the more small . On the other hand, PBM is boring will increase desire skipping class for students . _ Teacher to get it do detection as early as Possible to habit truant students , with _ do approach educative to truants _ as well as increase discipline the teaching , accompanied introspection and retrospection to method each other's teaching . Discussion with eye teachers lesson kind as well as senior/ expert teachers are very much needed. Don't only do action unilateral with throw error to student always , maybe system the teacher's own instruction is necessary revised and improved . Or maybe a manufacturing strategy questions / tests as well as system the evaluation need reviewed back . Don't lustful give a difficult test , however give a number of questions that can be done produce successful , so student No easy broken enthusiastic . Come closer your students so they can disclose necessary problems _ solved , especially those that are constraint learning / PBM. Behave haughty or scary or acting " haunted " in front of student it's not is ideal teacher attitude . Act wise in a way educative need preserved for the sake of creation climate positive socio -emotional , and action This No is lowering action _ teacher's authority .

- 4) Likes to daydream and lack concentrate in lesson , or often bother his friends during lesson , or Like clowning in class For interesting attention . The wisdom of the inner teacher matter This is with improve management strategies _ _ class as well as instructional strategies so that they can quick consolidate its PBM . With approach sociology education and guidance - counseling , can given appropriate therapy _ as well as return _ _ condition student For return respect to PBM. When it happens obstacle physiological or medical , then need done follow referral to doctor For find the cause until provide appropriate diagnosis and therapy , so can return concentration learn it . To kid who likes it clowning in class , given chance For displays his abilities joke around in opportunities certain , with notes No can do it anywhere place , esp in PBM. Even when maybe , the teacher can slipped - right in the lesson academic jokes _ so that exceed ability students who like it clowning that . Furthermore It is hoped that teachers can with fast and precise apply / put into practice knowledge - huan as well as his skills from preservice and inservice training , for the success of PBM as well achieved

objective specified education _ with full wisdom as well as unemotional .

5) Next ways deterrence as done _ in family , especially relevant ones , can also done in environment school . In case This creativity Teachers are highly expected for their service to education .

c. In the environment public

In the environment broad and complex society (includes _ family and school), participation all over element related parties are highly expected , namely religious leaders , government region , ruler local , enforcer law , power medical and paramedic , psychologist / psychiatrist , educator , youth organization , organization women , and so on integrated and individually without _ differentiate ethnicity , class , religion, position , strata, and so on shoulder not quite enough answer and answer automatic must feel called bear and own not quite enough answer in a way proportional For do follow deterrence in a way wise and responsible answer , without selfless personal / group , and non-business .

Based on complaints society , especially teachers and parents , about difficulty they in control and improve _ _ will Study students / children Because the more increasing TVRI and Private TV shows , then perhaps need reviewed return about schedule of broadcast programs on television , including government / private radio . During study hours (07.00 - 12.00 and 18.00 - 20.00) you should aired / broadcast events of a nature academic or support education , news , and information important , so children / students can do activity Study in a way more intensive . That thing intended to be able to improved quality source Power man in a way more programmed.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion that can be taken from study This are :

1. Mischief children / adolescents in the environment around UNNES.
2. Various effort For ward off mischief child / adolescent in a way wise , precise and efficient

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